

Environmental Bio-acoustic Monitoring

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Project Objectives

With human development increasing across Australia and the world, broad-scale baseline recordings are imperative to determine the current state of ecosystems before they vanish. There are many advantages to using automated technologies such as recording sounds to monitor the environment. The ability of scientists to remotely and passively record these sounds offers the opportunity to capture a great deal of environmental and biological data to facilitate a greater understanding of the biology of these animals, simply by listening. Animal sounds can reveal the identity, behaviour, location, number, and ecology of vocalising species, and long-term recordings distributed over broad spatial scales allow for a continuous opportunity to simultaneously survey the wildlife of Australia at a continent-wide scale, providing a level of data that would be prohibitive in cost and effort with nearly any other survey method.

Bioacoustics is also a scalable technology that provides large scale long-term monitoring for a relatively low equipment and deployment cost. Bioacoustics can capture information about the environment from all directions around a deployed sensor, which is an advantage over other non-invasive monitoring technologies, such as the use of cameras.

The data sets and tools provided by a national bioacoustic array will provide a unique resource that will place Australian researchers at the forefront of bioacoustics research. The aim of the workshop was to serve as a first step towards developing a continentally/nationally integrated programme of bioacoustic sampling, analysis and data sharing to identify causes of biodiversity change within the context of the wider ecosystem. The workshop studied questions related to various components of national bioacoustics array, and its potential impact on environmental science and policy. One of the outcomes of the workshop was to develop a preliminary plan for deploying this infrastructure on a continental scale.

Major Findings

There is currently a gap in knowledge and infrastructure for bioacoustic monitoring in Australia. Spatial and temporal coverage is lacking and the collection and management of acoustic information is absent or ad hoc. Acoustic data is yet to be combined with other ancillary environmental information and variables for appropriately ground truthing the results and synthesising the information into ecosystem-wide findings.

It was proposed in the workshop that the deployment of a coordinated national infrastructure for bioacoustics and the development of an enduring national library of bioacoustics data is required. There is a need for investment in the synthesis of bioacoustic data with other environmental data to maximise the value from investing in a bioacoustics infrastructure. This will require standardisation of data collection methods, the development of cyber-infrastructure for data exchange and the consistent use of proven statistical methods applied on a continental scale.

The specific outcomes of the workshop comprised an operational framework to enable the deployment of a network of bioacoustic monitoring systems, manage and access the observations, interpret the general and specific information in the data and specifically address elements of biological diversity, ecological disturbance, species presence and abundance and first arrival events.

A national acoustic data service will provide access to two types of data sets:

(i) The first is data obtained from a continental-scale deployment of acoustics sensors (a national acoustic array). The aim will be to provide data in an open, standard and sharable data platform that enables maximum use by acoustics researchers.

(ii) The second type is archival and current data sets that are maintained by independent research groups around Australia. The aim of the data service, in this case, is to ensure the discoverability of data, the inter-operability with existing platforms and compatibility with existing data sets.

Products and Outcomes

Members of the group will co-author a white paper that discusses the merits of deploying a national continental-scale bioacoustic array. The white paper will consider the various components of the array, its potential impact on environmental science and policy and propose a staged approach to setting up the array.

Members of the group are editing a special issue of Ecological Informatics (<http://www.journals.elsevier.com/ecological-informatics/>) on bioacoustics. The special issue will cover the major four topics of bioacoustic research: acoustic sensors, data formats and exchange, data analysis tools and environmental applications of acoustic data.

A prototype data portal has been developed (Figure 1) to demonstrate the functions and value of a national bioacoustic data service. This data portal will provide rudimentary tools for data access and sharing as well as the ability to provide data collected by different groups in a standard format from a number of locations across Australia.

Welcome!
Acoustic sensors provide an effective means for monitoring biodiversity at large spatial and temporal scales. The Australian National Acoustic Biodiversity Monitoring Programme aims to provide the research community with a portal to national scale acoustic sensor data repositories, and a suite of tools to perform analysis and reporting on these data.

About Bush.fm
The repository aims to allow researchers and citizen scientists to access, describe and analyse audio recordings on a national scale.

Contact
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Bush.fm is collaboration between: QUT, JAMES COOK UNIVERSITY AUSTRALIA, TERN

Figure 1: Bush.fm acoustic portal used by the Australian Supersite Network as a prototype for a national environmental acoustics data service

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science and management?

The deployment of bioacoustic monitoring systems on a wide scale and integration of collected data would significantly address the current lack of practical methodology for monitoring Australia's biodiversity. Many different species are frequently detected within single recordings. Sound recordings can be used to establish

species inventories at different locations, and those behaviours that these taxa are engaging in (such as reproductive activity, predator-prey interactions, etc).

A national bioacoustic array will be able to provide real-time information to policy makers and researchers about the state of the environment using acoustic sensors. This, in turn, will provide an information base for biodiversity assessment (species-specific) and inform policymakers and land managers about the health of the environment. An acoustic data bank that achieves comprehensive coverage over a long period of time can potentially provide trends for ecosystem diversity, detect the arrival and departure of invasive species and identify reference sites for healthy ecosystems.

Above: Sensor deployment on Groote Island.